

RESEARCH STRATEGY

"value-based care"[Title/Abstract] OR "value-based healthcare"[Title/Abstract] OR "value-based health care"[Title/Abstract] OR "valuebased care"[Title/Abstract] OR "value-based care"[Title/Abstract] OR "value-based healthcare"[Title/Abstract] OR "value-based health care"[Title/Abstract] OR "VBHC"[Title/Abstract] OR "Value-based"[Title/Abstract] OR "valuebased"[Title/Abstract]

AND

"polic*"[Title/Abstract] OR "strateg*"[Title/Abstract] OR "intervention*"[Title/Abstract] OR "program*"[Title/Abstract] OR "manag*"[Title/Abstract]

AND

"organizational change*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Change management"[Title/Abstract] OR "Redesign"[Title/Abstract] OR "transformation*"[Title/Abstract] OR "implement*"[Title/Abstract]